

Spatial aspects of de-radicalisation processes in Florence

D9.1 City report

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and wider social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young adults in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) with the goal of moving towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. Our intention is to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, which include a sense of being victimised; a sense of being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures; and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Iraq, Jordan, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad LABs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation states adapt to new security challenges. The process of mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts will be crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that processes of radicalisation often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national frameworks of justice. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation will be central to the project's aims.

Executive Summary/Abstract

Florence shows a rather plural public (and civic) space, and its social, political, and associative richness potentially renders it a quite inclusive space. Nevertheless, Florence historical and cultural heritage is a well-established pattern of the city identity, which might become *exclusive*, vis-à-vis *other* identities. As it is well known, also, Florence has a long history of tourism and given its small dimensions, it belongs to a group of historic cities where tourists – who are often regarded as a resource – might become a risk for public space. In fact, in this regard, processes of gentrification of the cityscape are becoming more and more visible, progressively undermining free and equal access to spaces and places. Outside the most aesthetically glamorous part of the city centre, different cultures and nationalities compete for a tiny place in which to meet or gather. This also implies some kind of internal segmentation of the same shared public space, which further suggests an exclusive way of perceiving the city. The public space in Florence thus appears to be a place that is denied or neglected in terms of its enjoyment as well as the opportunities to foster civil and social interaction. Conceiving its cityscape without tourism is quite a difficult task; however, examples of best practices and ‘resistance’ to the city’s massification can be detected, albeit beyond the city’s “economic” and wealthy core.

1. Introduction

The present report will address the Florence cityscape and its peculiarities in order to provide an in-depth assessment of the local level. Indeed, in accordance with the WP9 aims, an analysis of the local level will involve an investigation into *whether* and *how* social dynamics concerning the public space as a sphere of encounters enable actual negotiations over differences and plural claims. In this regard, a relevant aspect also concerns *which* barriers prevent equal access to the public space (in general, Baum-Snow *et al.*, 2018), along with *where* and *why* this may occur.

For the purposes of D. Rad, the relationships between alienation, marginalisation and (more or less violently expressed) grievances are crucial points too. The public arena, as a space for substantive participation beyond the borders of 'citizenship', may well become an exclusive place, in which only 'best' or 'selected' idea(l)s can be shared, discussed and endorsed (Davidson, 2023). Thus, the inclusiveness of public space can be challenged by several different factors and actors, which may vary considerably according to local and regional (as well as national) specificities (Amin, 2006; Carmona, Bento & Gabrieli, 2023).

In this respect, Florence represents an interesting framework worth investigating further. In fact, in the urban environment multiple realities, identities and spaces coexist. This is obviously not peculiar to Florence, and different local communities in Italy (and beyond) present these recurrent features. Nonetheless, as will be argued throughout this report, Florence interestingly appears as a Janus-faced reality, where the public and the private dimension of the same space do not merge perfectly, since this duality fosters micro conflicts, divergent representations and challenging experiences (in general, Fincher & Jacobs, 1998). In particular, in this context, a major role is played by the huge presence of tourism on the one hand, and the (consequent?) gentrification of its cultural and historical heritage on the other (see De Carlo & Dubini, 2010).

Despite the fascinating history and urban 'landscape' boasted by Florence, the outcomes of the research emphasise the 'pathological' effects of overtourism and how the latter impacts the different ways of experiencing the city and living in the city. Moreover, the extensive presence of tourism in certain areas has not only affected broad access to and enjoyment of those spaces, but also shaped the physiognomy (and 'aesthetics') of Florence's cityscape accordingly.

Consequently, as we will try to show in the following sections, we assume that the public space in Florence is a place that is generally denied by tourism, in terms of its enjoyment as well as the opportunities to foster civil and social interaction.

Hence, all the abovementioned aspects will be thoroughly analysed and explored in the following sections. First, after some notes on methodology, a description of the spatial characteristics and of the city context will be provided, also taking into account relevant best practices and contested areas in the overall local framework. Second, a summary of the outcomes of the D.Rad LABs (I and II) will be offered through an analysis of the selected case studies. Finally, we will set forth some policy recommendations relying on the research findings, followed by some conclusive remarks about the public space as depicted in our focus on Florence.

2. Description of methods

For our analysis we chose to focus on Florence as a contended public space. In this regard, therefore, an investigation of various aspects of its intrinsic duality was deemed essential in order to convey a general picture of the cityscape. The study emphasises the ‘pathological’ effects of overtourism in relatively small town and how the tourism impacts the different ways of experiencing the city and living in the city. Indeed, Florence’s private and public ‘facades’ offer interesting insights into *whether* they mutually interact and actually integrate. Precisely, this Janus-faced nature can be detected also as far as (really free) places and their enjoyment are concerned and therefore plays a key-role in the research. Therefore, the first methodological challenge was to identify the public space in a city overwhelmed by tourism.

The abovementioned assumptions on the ‘duality’ of the Florentine public space were methodologically ‘tested’ in a twofold perspective. First, we conducted five interviews, involving academia, municipal institutions and civil society actors in order to benefit from a multidisciplinary approach towards a challenging topic and to identify or uncover shortcomings or concealed conflicts. Second, we organized two participatory focus group (LABs) where we ask some question to experts or stakeholders with the help of question cards: LAB I (March 27, 2023) was held in a well-known San Frediano district meeting point (*Associazione la Rondinella – Il Torrino*) with institutional representatives, along with civil, sport, and social associations; whereas LAB II (June 19, 2023) took place in *Piazza Torquato Tasso*, in the same San Frediano district, with young adult residents. We thus “embedded” our LABs in the same context we chose as a best practice, preferring direct interaction with people, identities and realities encountering each other in the same public space we assume as ‘contended’ and ‘contested’, in order to evaluate social dynamics (and paradigms) through ‘immersion’ in the context.

3. Description of spatial characteristics and city context

After conducting a review of literature critically discussing the ‘urban’ quality of living in an area highly frequented by tourists (see Borocz, 1992; Angeloni, 2013; Bernini *et al.* 2014), we sought to develop the analysis further by taking into account opportunities for inclusion and free (and/or democratic-participatory) use of the public space in Florence.

Florence, with its 369,000 inhabitants and population of over 998,000 within its metropolitan area (Ufficio Comunale di Statistica, 2020), is a medium-sized city in central Italy and the capital of the Tuscany region. Over the past 2 decades, Florence has not experienced any notable population loss or growth, although a slight growth can be seen each year due to immigration. In 2022, there were 6,333 births and 12,666 deaths, so the natural balance is negative. However, there was an increase of 9,646 immigrants, resulting in a total growth of 2,914 people. Foreign residents now make up 16.3% (59,218) of the overall population.

Due to its cultural richness, Florence has a long history of tourism dating back the “Grand Tour”, of which Florence has been an inescapable milestone for centuries. The entire historic centre was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List in 1982 and since the early 1980s it has been experiencing very large influxes of tourists, which has caused several issues for tourists and locals alike. The number of tourists rose to 15 million staying overnight per year in 2022. Also, an estimated 32 million “day trippers” visit Florence every year. On Christmas Eve 2022 alone there were 365,000 visitors, basically matching the entire resident population in number. Both overnight tourists and day trippers visit the relatively small city centre. Given its small dimensions, tourism might become a threat for public space (European Commission Report, 2000).

Over the recent years, in particular after the health emergency of 2020, the city administration has set a tourist-oriented *policy*. The public space, once restricted due to Covid-19 reasons, was further eroded by restaurants and cafés with outdoor seating. In fact, in a ‘resilient’ response perspective and in order to enhance the local economy (severely affected by lockdowns), *more* public space was assigned to private activities, with low fees or directly for free. Nonetheless, despite their “social” relevance in creating spaces for gathering and sharing, they also prevented public and free enjoyment of the very same places, which may well be populated in rather different ways (and according to rather diverse social paradigms). Thus, the end of the pandemic restrictions did not lead to a re-appropriation of public space, but rather furthered its privatisation to (paradoxically) enable social interaction *and* “social distancing” at the same time. Public space becomes *really* free outside the most aesthetically glamorous part of the city centre, where different cultures and nationalities compete for a tiny place in which to meet or gather. This also implies some kind of internal segmentation of the same shared public space, which becomes, for some reasons, also an identitarian way of living in and defining the public space itself.

In Florence all the different layers regarding the enjoyment of space, the conflicts, the encounters and claims of belonging can be evaluated through the city’s different geographies, depending on the specific characteristics of each space *within* the same place, i.e. the Florence cityscape as a whole.

The areas of the city centre we decided to focus on for the present report are San Lorenzo, via Palazzuolo (Porta al Prato), San Frediano and Santo Spirito. The latter two are close to each other and are thus commonly considered as practically the same area; however, the former is an example of best practices, the latter of a contested area.

All of these spaces are experiencing:

- 1) a large concentration of foreign residents;
- 2) a gentrification of their spaces;
- 3) a large impact on their everyday cultural life due to mass tourism;
- 4) efforts and attempts of some residents' associations and local social services to preserve community cohesion, whereas the role of the city administration there is generally rather ambiguous.

(Areas under investigation. Source: www.aeroportodifirenze.com)

Via Palazzuolo (in the Porta al Prato area) is located between the Santa Maria Novella train Station and San Frediano. This area does not feature many tourist attractions and a part of the street is well known for the highest concentration of residents with migration backgrounds and ethnic shops.

San Frediano is a vital multicultural neighbourhood; it has always been a poor part of the town, inhabited by craftsmen and laborers. Even today, it is home to a mixed population of

the Florentine working class and immigrants coming from the global south as well as international students and/or western expats, such as British, American and French people who married a Florentine.

3.1. Description of three “best practice” areas

The first area we focused on is San Lorenzo. During the day, the streets are almost completely occupied by leather and clothing stalls in a crowded market (the vast majority of stalls belong to foreign people, such as Bangladeshi), but in the nighttime the streets are empty and lonely. Due to a high concentration of foreign residents from East Africa, Bangladesh and South America, San Lorenzo is gaining increasing attention from the city administration. In San Lorenzo, indeed, community LABs are often organised: *inter alia*, participatory meetings to discuss issues, addressed to social actors belonging to different institutions and aimed at promoting local inclusive practices and actions¹. Conferences are also organised spontaneously or – albeit infrequently – by the city government², in which a group of residents is asked to reach a compromise about the implementation of some projects in the area. In the San Lorenzo neighbourhood, residents and foreign communities act in an organised manner. Their meetings are often spontaneous and reflect a bottom-up perspective, though there are no long-term fixed projects.

A very similar situation can be found in the Porta al Prato area and, in particular, in Via Palazzuolo, where the concentration of more than 20 ethnic groups might well give rise to a conflictual situation. In this context, the association “Anelli Mancanti” is the most effective as far as inclusion and (substantive) de-radicalisation are concerned. The organisation offers language lessons, primarily to school children with a migration background, along with other cultural activities, and has thus become a reference point for many immigrant families. Here (paradoxically), the redevelopment strategy implemented by the city administration has had a positive effect: the only square present in the area was “assigned” to a 4-star hotel in order to upgrade part of the street, while helping to restyle the urban aesthetics.

In the San Frediano neighbourhood, a similar inclusion strategy has emerged from local roundtables and participatory meetings, representing an opportunity for new partnerships between area stakeholders and the municipal institutions. Also in San Frediano this roundtable are often spontaneous or organized by local groups (such as an anti-systemic left wing community), reflecting a bottom-up perspective. Fruitful debates among residents and workers with rather different backgrounds have been conceived as a tool for

¹ For instance, the “Consorzio dello Storico Mercato Centrale”, the residents association “Insieme per San Lorenzo” and the Association “I Sopravvissuti del San Lorenzo” created a participatory maintenance and management net on WhatsApp in order to keep safe the urban heritage of the area and to report inadequacies and criminal offences.

² <https://www.lanazione.it/firenze/cronaca/via-al-piano-contro-il-degrado-1.6274390>. An interesting example is also the “camminata di quartiere” (neighbourhood walk): the aim is to observe and record how life in the neighbourhood unfolds at different times of the day and night and to bring out useful indications for improving urban and social quality and coexistence (<https://www.controradio.it/firenze-camminata-di-quartiere-a-san-lorenzo/>).

strengthening and expanding their networks and identifying new shared strategies to preserve community engagement, with particular regard to urban social spaces and the two large community parks (one of them is the main square, piazza Tasso).

Several public community events take place close to the square, playing a crucial role in maintaining the area 'alive'. There are also a number of neighbourhood facilities such as the "Ardiglione" or "Nidiaci" park, a historic place behind the Carmine church (in which there is "Iudoteca", or a large room with toys and games where children play), a community canteen (*Bagni popolari*), accommodations for homeless people (*Albergo popolare*) and a community gym set up by "I Bianchi" organisation, which attracts many young adults, most of whom with a migration background. The group, also known as the "Whites" in English, is one of the four historical district teams that participate in the *Calcio Storico Fiorentino* (historical football) tournament in Florence.³ Their headquarters are located in San Frediano. As will be confirmed by the LAB I findings, the Bianchi team's main goal is not only to win the tournament and bring pride to their district (therefore they undergo rigorous training to prepare for the matches, which are both physically and mentally intense), but also to keep the history and social identity of the neighbourhood alive. At the gym, young adults are asked to get involved in the social activities of and for the area.

Sports are a particularly relevant field for inclusion and deradicalisation in San Frediano, as they help in the development of a shared culture of social (and safety) cooperation. In addition to the Bianchi's community gym, a free public multipurpose sports ground (basketball and football), easily accessible to anyone, can be found in piazza Tasso. This facility is an ideal space for promoting inclusiveness every day through sports and leisure activities, a place where kids from both Italian and migration backgrounds can be seen playing together.

3.2. Description of three contested areas

As for our interview outcomes, tourism was identified as one of the major challenges to urban quality, both in terms of opportunities for inclusion and the free use of public space, in particular because of the tourist-oriented city economy. According to some stakeholders "there is no point in talking about urban space in Florence: the squares, the gardens are now marginal".⁴ Squares become the places of "the powerless: the elderly, children and migrants. On the one hand it makes them less usable and worsens their aesthetic appearance, on the other hand the city government is not too interested in guaranteeing their use, because the users do not have effective political influence".⁵

According to many interviewees, Santo Spirito (the area contiguous with San Frediano) and San Lorenzo are *denied space*, being highly tourist-oriented areas lacking common spaces

³ An early form of rugby played by amateurs 6 times a year; every district has its own team: the *Bianchi* represent Santo Spirito/San Frediano areas.

⁴ Interview n. 3, see Annex I.

⁵ Interview n.2, *ibidem*.

for residents to gather. That is why public spaces in these areas “need to be experienced at night: during the day they are occupied by tourism”.⁶

This is particularly true for San Lorenzo, where shopping life makes this area very dynamic, but also where street/market stalls have occupied the entire area surface, although at night it becomes an empty and potentially unsafe neighbourhood.

Santo Spirito is also experiencing social fragmentation within the urban space (as social services are concentrated in more peripheral areas) and gentrification processes leading to the appropriation of these areas by elites or tourists. This polarisation may inevitably foster resentment and tension . An example is provided by the attempt to limit the so called *movida*⁷: in the summer of 2022, the municipal authority decided to barricade the churchyard in the main square, thereby preventing many young adults from enjoying the public space without offering any alternative solution. Many experts believed that at night the outdoor seating areas allocated to restaurants and pubs are also contributing to the loss of public space. The Municipal Councillor of Welfare and Integration, Sara Funaro, also interviewed as an expert, stressed that such outdoor facilities should not be considered a form of privatisation, since they offer a service to citizens, along with an “upgrading of the area”. In this regard, they rather allow “a better use of these spaces by providing a place to sit” (though this implies that the municipality is unable or unwilling to provide public facilities in turn).

The problem of Via Palazzuolo (in the Porta al Prato area) is connected with the lack of public space to take advantage of. As the association “Anelli Mancanti” pointed out, no public squares, no social services such as libraries or sporting clubs are planned by the city government. A cloister, which is now at the city’s disposal and would supply suitable space, is yet not exploitable. This restricts the possibilities for Anelli Mancanti and other associations to offer their no-profit based services.

4. In-depth analysis of the case study

In light of the above, we chose to focus our research on the San Frediano area in particular, where we also planned and set up both our D.Rad LABs. In San Frediano one can find a well-balanced concentration of community services and social housing and parks with sports facilities, as well as a strong awareness among residents about the need to preserve the authenticity and social inclusion of the area. Therefore, it can be depicted as a positive model of integration, able to prevent and to counteract radicalisation.

Focusing on this space was deemed essential chiefly for two reasons. On the one hand, San Frediano represents a quite central place in Florence, rather close to the tourist core of the city, while at the same time maintaining its ‘particularism’ and (unique) identity. On the other hand, it embodies a place of ‘resistance’, not only against the abovementioned

⁶ Interview n.2 and n.3, *ibidem*.

⁷ Spontaneous and crowded social gathering in the streets late in the night, not directly related with the private social space of the street.

gentrification of the Florence urban physiognomy, but also vis-à-vis its (internal) social composition and (historically) identitarian attitude. As far as the first point is concerned, indeed, in San Frediano quite strongly established and well-rooted solidaristic networks have been present for decades. This has also meant preserving its cooperative structure, where people living in the neighbourhood are far from tourism dynamics, though spatially close to the city centre. As for the second aspect, closely linked to the former, identity and (local) culture have become sites of (successfully resolved) confrontation and challenges, especially regarding in-group/out-group dynamics, as will be explained later on.

Hence, in this context, both encounters and exchanges occur in multiple ways. Also, a massive presence of social activities and pervasive action of social services as well as of civil associations can be observed. These circumstances could maybe be seen from a common standpoint, as causes and effects together. Furthermore, encounters can be considered from a double perspective too: San Frediano is a space (and a place) where people meet in a substantive way and engage in discussion to further improve the 'quality' of life in the neighbourhood. Namely, it represents a place where competing claims arise and are settled. To this extent, its cultural homogeneity has been jeopardised by the changing social structure, due to mutual exchanges fostered by migrations and non-residents choosing to permanently stay in this district. Although this transformation initially gave rise to tensions and conflict, nowadays a horizontal (and rather equal) enjoyment of the public space can be found.

4.1. Summary of D.Rad LAB I

The D.Rad LAB I took place in a well-known San Frediano neighbourhood meeting point, the premises of the "Associazione Rondinella, il Torrino", where diverse civil society actors usually gather and specifically met on the occasion of our LAB. In particular, we hosted representatives from different associations: Angeli della Città, Incontriamoci sull'Arno, Confluenze, Giardino dell'Ardiglione, and Calcio Storico "I Bianchi", all of them constantly operating in San Frediano with several individual and joint projects for the community at large.

When we submitted our Question Cards, one crucial point came immediately to the surface, namely the *genuine* creation of a support network, through which all the associations active in San Frediano naturally cooperate (and have collaborated in the past) in a rather informal way, without external pressures or (public/private) constraints. In the area, public free food delivery, public toilets (once also including showers) and a popular free hostel for homeless people have always been active and working for the people's common good. At the same time, no actual contested or contended places (or spaces) have been able to develop.

As for the structure of Florence in general, the Janus-faced nature of this district, described as a space with "lots of energy and lots of need" at the same time, is likewise apparent. It paradigmatically represents a place where solidarity and demands inherently meet and are met. Additionally, the deep 'territorial' roots have been defined as the basic and essential factor underlying the forms of social gathering peculiar to San Frediano. Not surprisingly, this crucial fact has represented both a source of resistance and of transformation of the

very same place, also through the key elements of identity and claims. Precisely, the latter – the progressive (and inevitable) development of the concept of the public space itself, as well as the negotiation of belonging – represents a fundamental stage in changing the way San Frediano is experienced and how people currently live there, taking into account *how* it has changed in the process as well.

In fact, until the 1950's San Frediano could be defined as a rather closed space, a place where exclusively residents lived (and met) and which showed a strong identitarian pattern⁸ vis-à-vis other neighbourhoods, even if nearby. Its particularism and differences were thus considered profound and substantive. Slowly, this form of social exclusivism was eroded, and everything gradually but profoundly changed: people, their behaviours and 'mores' as well as forms of and ideas about social gathering. A good example can be provided by the already mentioned, well-rooted, tradition of "historical football". The latter has a past of violent, conflictual and fierce competition. Over the years, a new idea and image have progressively matured: a tradition carried forward with openness, despite being rooted in the neighbourhood, devoted to the new generations with a different vision of society. In the teams, people not only from San Frediano but from all over the world, also with diversified political ideas, interact on an equal basis through fair 'rules of the game', bringing young adults closer through a sense of belonging to a group, of sharing, of friendship, which is also seen as a way to transform violence itself. Gyms have thus evolved into spaces where many kids learn sports and respect for differences, as well as the importance of learning to 'lose' (games). Historical football has thus been able to turn a divisive and violent practice into a means for bringing together all the different energies that live in the neighbourhood.

The latter, however, has often been free from political affiliations and claims in a general sense, providing for support broadly across the community according to needs. In this respect, the focus on youth has represented a key element, from a double perspective. On the one hand, social activities have prominently been addressed to young adults and aimed at providing spaces for their cultural and individual development; on the other, young adults themselves have been involved in favour of disadvantaged or needy groups, for instance by helping in everyday activities, such as shopping for food, household chores, and the personal hygiene of disabled people, *inter alia*. Thus, the San Frediano district shows a tradition of proactive and substantive solidarity, which has also been defined by one of our LAB participants as 'structural', meaning that the urban fabric as well, due to the presence of facilities and their effective functioning, has somehow nurtured these bonds of mutuality among the people living there. Interestingly, this tradition, even though rooted in the past, has transformed over time, along with the transformation of the neighbourhood's social composition. Whereas at first only Italian residents were involved in the social activities and received support, collective care is currently more focused on families of foreigners and children and includes activities such as providing legal assistance with residence permits or offering free afterschool classes. Quite paradigmatically, one participant highlighted that "this is how San Frediano *is*: while the specific characteristics may vary, it historically

⁸ "After the war, those who worked in San Frediano, were born in San Frediano, lived in San Frediano, and married in San Frediano, only with *sanfredianini*".

maintains its solidaristic core, changing and evolving according to circumstances”. This circumstance has been viewed as the main foundation of natural and spontaneous dialogue and (equal) interaction among the different ‘segments’ making up the social composition of San Frediano, where multiple identities and backgrounds merge in the promotion of a common ground (and a shared space).

Moreover, this characteristic of a “sphere” of encounters became even more visible during the COVID-19 pandemic, since thanks to the inherent ‘horizontal’ solidarity, nobody was left alone: everyone received support, especially those living in isolation with (additional) difficulties. Inside a youth centre, a shared space was created where several services were offered. This space still stands and has since become a gathering place; new projects are also growing out of it. In San Frediano, even in tough times, people meet and “recognise each other” and are always starting up new projects linked to solidarity and coming together, as part of an important historical legacy.

In this regard, another relevant aspect comes into the picture, as stressed during the LAB. In San Frediano there has been neither the establishment nor construction of specific mono-ethnic groups. The population living there appears mixed and heterogeneous, as symbolically represented by the highly diversified composition of primary school classes. In this regard, a critical insight has been assessed as well: foreign adults are less keen on actually interact with the San Frediano community, somehow remaining *excluded* as their own choice. This sometimes translates also into an *exclusion* from the San Frediano solidaristic networks, due to the circumstance that needs or demands may remain unexpressed, unknown, thus ‘out of reach’. As far as residents’ (exclusive) identity is concerned, on the contrary, the “traditional” social and cultural affinities, as well as *pastness*, did not prevent the development of an enlarged concept of ‘community’ with a huge inter- and multicultural potential (to be further monitored in its possible future transformations). This means taking the historical legacy and remoulding it according to current times, that is, taking “responsibility for the past not solely as a past history since it is the place where ancestors lived, but also because it is the place where we raise our children together and create a future in and for this place, as a collective way to take care of the past and to defend it”. For these reasons, San Frediano has been able to recreate and re-found a world of human relationships, avoiding alienation and marginalisation, through the negotiation of past, present and future belonging.

4.2. Summary of D.Rad LAB II

The young adults involved in LAB II consistently identified Piazza Torquato Tasso and the whole district of San Frediano as a multicultural, inclusive space. They still consider San Frediano as a “poor part of town”. Furthermore, they confirmed that this area ensures an environment where individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds feel valued, respected, and – most importantly – have equal opportunities to participate in and contribute to the local community. A man with a migration background said that for him, being a part of the San

Frediano community means that everyone, regardless of their cultural or ethnic background, can fully participate in social, economic, and cultural aspects of neighbourhood life.

Several times the participants used the words “family”, “community” and even “my world” in describing San Frediano, which in their eyes is a micro-city within Florence. Hence, an area where an entire existence might be fulfilled: “you don’t need to go to other parts of the city, everything is here”. The young adults attending LAB II, including those with a migration background, not only felt accepted in San Frediano, but they also experienced a sense of comradeship, of belonging which is mostly based on sports and the sharing of a common space in an atmosphere of equality. The oldest of them noted that the area had become increasingly diverse over the years (particularly compared to when they went to elementary school): on the one hand, people from different cultural backgrounds were starting to settle; on the other hand, the increase in tourism gave rise to a risk of gentrification.

In general, the majority of the young adults described the neighbourhood as “full of contrasts”, but in a positive sense: in Piazza Tasso and in the streets “you can see homeless persons, youth, sophisticated couples and, finally, families with children, either Italian or with a migration background, all at the same time, in the same place”. As they recognised, many of the foreign people living in the public space are residents (and not tourists): not only families with a migration background, but also international students, artists, or people who married a Florentine that decided to live in San Frediano.

Although the presence of tourism is not (yet) overwhelming, the interaction in the focus group raised a significant issue regarding gentrification. Almost every person expressed concerns due to an increasing presence of tourism in the area. It was argued that the influx of tourists contributes to an increase in the prices of real estate, rents and, in general, the cost of living for local residents: a high demand for housing, restaurants, goods and services are driving up prices, making it more difficult for residents, especially those with lower incomes, to afford living in the area. This is slowly modifying the “popular” nature of San Frediano, driving away poorer families, as one young woman stressed.

The COVID-19 pandemic did not really alter the cohesion in the area: on the contrary, services to people in need increased.

In general, in the neighbourhood’s daily life, there is no interest at all in geopolitical issues such as the war in Ukraine, the economic crisis or the climate crisis. Many of the demonstrations and community meetings express local political demands (fighting gentrification, displacement, etc.). There is also a disregard for or distrust towards politics. The feeling is that political actors do not represent the interests of young adults, and that they rely for the most part on the good practices of private actors and volunteers operating in the area.

The young adults gathered in San Frediano agreed on the need to “save” this area from real estate speculation, gentrification, and the city administration’s rhetoric about the “most

beautiful city in the world”, which leads to a sort of institutional indifference towards local commercial activities and non-profit-based services. According to some participants, local politics does not properly acknowledge how the overwhelming tourist industry may affect the small and family-run businesses in the area, which are now more and more dependent and over-reliant on tourism-related activities.

They also identified some public spaces that they consider crucial in the area’s everyday life: The “Ardiglione” or “Nidiaci” garden as a safe place for children when they were younger and also a place for their parents to meet. The “Rondinella”, a large green area in front of the river where young adults can relax during the summer and, of course, Piazza Tasso, with its sports grounds, benches, the “Pietro Thuar” city library and the surrounding bars.

According to those interviewed, one of the most influential actors present in this public space that shape the daily life of Piazza Tasso and San Frediano in general, is the already mentioned association “I Bianchi”. One of the Bianchi team’s objectives is to keep the history and social identity of a neighbourhood alive. The association owns a neighbourhood gym, a fitness facility designed to serve the needs of members of the San Frediano community (part of the gym staff has a migration background). Many of the young adults attending the LAB are also gym members (some of them doing boxing, others rugby) and they stressed that attending the gym also implies social duties: they are asked to be involved in volunteer work in the area, such as overseeing activities in the Nidiaci garden or helping families facing difficult circumstances.

The area is considered safe, with no concern at all regarding personal physical welfare.

Finally, in response to the question as to how public space could be improved, the majority did not have an answer. After some time, some of them suggested focusing on designing spaces that better accommodate their range of interests: creating an open-air gym in Piazza Tasso or at La Rondinella, installing a piano in Piazza Tasso (the person who suggested that is a musician), or building more sports grounds and swimming pools. It was also suggested that the area could be enriched with concerts and other social activities, since currently almost all of the events sponsored by the city government are aimed at promoting Santo Spirito, the neighbouring district.

4.3. Summary of the case study

The San Frediano district can boast a long tradition of proactive and substantive solidarity and has emerged as the most welcoming district in the whole territory of Florence. The geography of solidarity has been adjusted and accommodated according to new requests and a transcultural concept of local ‘citizenship’. It historically maintains that aspect of self-management, because it is endowed with associations working in the area that try to create spaces in which to make integration and inclusion effective, or in any case, to foster mutual understanding.

This has meant providing residents, as well as people from 'outside', with a safe place to stay, integrating them into the texture of the area, while at the same time not assimilating their way of experiencing and living in the city. This undoubtedly represents a fruitful way of conceiving social inclusion and preventing the public space from becoming inaccessible to minorities and exclusive. Additionally, *sharing* the public space also means framing it with a *shared* strategy, in which people are actively involved and play a dynamic and crucial role, attested by direct participation in the public arena.

5. Analysis and policy recommendations

A situation of contended space emerges from the analysis carried out so far. Along with a predominant focus on adapting the urban environment to the demands of tourism, we have witnessed a gradual but pervasive (and unstoppable) dismantling of public and open services. According to one of our interviewees, this process was somehow silent and concealed in order to prevent the city's residents from perceiving the taking away of space (including free space) as an institutional strategy.

The city centre, as a place for social gathering, has lost its function, also marking an intangible boundary between a private 'monopolistic' sphere on the one hand, and a fragmented (and conflictual) public space on the other. As a potential competitive sphere, where identities are challenged, challenge each other and confront each other in a framework of non-belonging. To this extent, encounters are quite asymmetric throughout all the Florence cityscapes. For instance, among foreigners, from one of the interviewees' points of view, a real sense of belonging to the city is actually lacking, and this is coupled with a closed attitude when it comes to interaction within the public space. This can be explained both by the exclusive identity Italians may seek to project in certain areas or to the loss of 'neighbourhood' identity in general terms.

As far as recommendations are concerned, the opportunity to conduct an in-depth analysis in San Frediano gave rise to fruitful insights into good practices and shared ways of enjoying and living in the city, notwithstanding its cultural and social fragmentation. As stressed by many experts, Municipal administration is rather reactive in Florence, but the promotion of horizontal management of neighbourhood communities should be strengthened. It has been shown how substantive cooperation can naturally lead to dialogue and interaction among different identities, claims and realities, which is certainly an added value for the administration too. This would also enable an actual 'integration', while at the same time preventing positions or situations – that in other contexts would be exacerbated or become conflictual – conducive to radicalisation. Secondly, whereas particularistic claims (and identities) should be protected as a fundamental part of a pluralist, equal and democratic society, based on diversity as a value in itself, a focus solely on identity, as in the Florence experience, can turn into something limiting and excluding. Thirdly, as the other side of the coin, the public space, even though or especially because it is segmented, should accommodate all the actors/stakeholders/identities moving and coexisting in it. The city may thus well become a 'community place', cooperating with institutions to further the general interest, as well as a space open to everyone. As the case of San Frediano has shown, a crucial role is played by civic and social associations which – also informally – act, unite and defend the common good, exchanging ideas and ideals in many fruitful ways.

6. Conclusions

As has been shown, how the public arena performs as an equal space is linked to the diverse, local, context-sensitive structuring of its spaces. Nevertheless, a selective participation in the public discourse can easily turn interactions between groups with different claims into conflicts among several viewpoints, especially, though not only, about how to use and enjoy the space itself (Routledge, 2010). Differentiating these spaces naturally affects social and cultural inclusion. In Florence, an exclusive way of perceiving the city has emerged. Tourism has played a crucial role in this regard, rendering some spaces inaccessible to everybody – either because they are elitist – or just linked to business interests – or because of gentrification.

Even residence status is tied to tourism: owners of restaurants, cafés, hotels or other commercial establishments themselves live far from the city centre, and the working class even further out from it (in general, Chapple, 2017). The urban space as a public sphere of encounters is thus shaped in concentric circles⁹: the core, which is ideally empty – apart from tourists – and is void of ‘public’ life, and the mono-ethnic spaces located around it. From the wealthy white Italians with their villas,¹⁰ to the other mono-ethnic spaces in which “others” live. This may foster micro us versus them dichotomies between different cultures, at the same time reflecting the macro social cleavage between the centre and other areas. Additionally, resentment towards these privileged groups can grow and spread, with a potentially radical(ised) concept of identity and belonging. In the light of the above, security instead of safety has been pivotal in framing the public space, deepening differences and consequently aggravating alienation and grievances (*inter alia*, Fincher & Iveson, 2012) among already “invisible” communities.

Nevertheless, some best practices informally and naturally developed in certain areas and neighbourhoods, suggesting that a space of resistance also exists there, where multiple identities and realities interact with each other, again through encounters and constant negotiation (Fincher & Iveson, 2008). In this regard, the active role of formal or informal associations has been decisive, also in counteracting social fragmentation (Harvey, 2009) and in shaping bonds of mutuality in difficult or tough times, reacting to challenges from within. The main critical point in Florence relates to the loss of a collective (shared, equal and public) identity of the city centre, a well-established process and a transformation that can hardly be reversed. Also taking into account that the exploitation of Florence’s cultural heritage, which has been one of the main factors contributing to gentrification, may soon also develop outside the city core, affecting other adjacent districts too. These dynamics have already been observed in San Frediano, our case study, where some silent – and by now gradual – erosion of the public space is threatening the ideal of living in a neighbourhood as a place devoted to and managed by the ‘people’. Though this has brought resistance from and protection of the very same place, other districts may show that this is not always the case.

⁹ As emerged during LAB I.

¹⁰ As emerged during LAB I.

Appendix I: Interviews

No.	Area of Expertise	Area of Employment	Interview Conducted
EI_Florence_1	Social Worker	Local NGO	24/11/2022
EI_Florence_2	Psychologist	University of Florence	19/12/2022
EI_Florence_3	Urbanistic experts	Private Foundation	11/01/2023
EI_Florence_4	Local Politics	Municipality Institution	23/01/2023
EI_Florence_5	Social Worker	Social Cooperation	15/03/2023

Appendix II: Florence through pictures

“Love your neighborhood: Defend it from Racism and Gentrification” (Building 15 m away from Piazza Tasso).

“Neighbourhood Lunch – every Sunday at 1:12 pm”

“Call for a neighbourhood assembly”

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